

Histopathological effects, Infection of *Alternaria alternata* on *Chrysanthemum parthenium* (L.) seeds and Disease Transmission

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Abstract

A total of 80 seed samples of *Chrysanthemum parthenium* seeds were collected from Rajasthan. Black discolouration of seeds mainly constituted by *Alternaria alternata*. 35 seed samples showed infection with an occurrence of 0.75 – 10.25%. In SBM incidence of fungus varied from 1-75% in untreated and 1-42% in pretreated seeds. The mycelium of pathogen was limited to outer layer of pericarp in asymptomatic (healthy) seeds but in symptomatic seeds all layers were infected and unidentified. The infected seedlings showed the symptoms initially appeared as browning and blacking of radical and later progressed towards cotyledonary leaves caused rotting.

Keywords

Chrysanthemum, Seed-borne fungi, Disease Transmission.

Introduction

Chrysanthemum parthenium plant belongs to the family 'Asteraceae'. It is bushy, aromatic, woody perennial plant with yellow, white, pink flower plant. It is growth both for its aesthetic and commercial value. The plant is grown for ornamental purposes throughout the greater parts of India (Anon, 1987). It is also cultivated as medicinal plant, insecticide and vermifuge (Oleg and Polunin, 1969).

The crop *Chrysanthemum parthenium* has huge economic importance. The fungus *Alternaria alternata* causes heavy loss to this crop. *Alternaria alternata* (Fr.) Keissler causes Alternaria leaf spot and blight disease of Chrysanthemum. Cox (1969) observed flower blight of chrysanthemum by *Alternaria alternata* caused heavy losses. The symptoms were delay in flower opening, resulting senescent tissues and petal necrosis. Cox (1969); Avallini, Dercode and Passerini (1992) reported flower blight of chrysanthemum caused by *Alternaria alternata* and associated with the seeds of the plant. Tammen (1965) noticed flower blight of chrysanthemum caused by *Alternaria sp.*; Singh *et al.* (2006) tested the chemical control of leaf spot disease of *Tagetes erecta* caused by *Alternaria sp.* Leaf spot of *Tagetes* plants was observed during in New Jersey affecting > 60% of the stock. A large spored, long beaked *Alternaria sp.* was isolated (Cotty, 1986). Prasad (1987) isolated endophytic seed mycoflora viz. *Alternaria alternata*, and *A.tenuissima* from the seeds of plants belonging to Asteraceae. Westcott (1971), found *Alternaria sp.* as a seed-borne fungi on *Chrysanthemum parthenium*. Isikov (1991) isolated *A.alternata* from 43 ornamental plants. *Alternaria alternata* is a seed-borne pathogen and caused leaf spot disease on many crops (Neergaard, 1977; Richardson, 1990). Schmidt (1958) observed leaf spot disease of Chrysanthemum maximum by caused *Alternaria chrysenthemi*. The pathogen affects all the green parts of the plant. Srinath and Sarwar (1965) reported the occurrence of *Alternaria teuissima*. A comprehensive information regarding to the seed-borne fungi of *Chrysanthemum parthenium* obtained by present study.

Objective of study

To determine the location of the pathogen in the infected seeds by histopathological studies.

Review of Literature

Two antagonistic fungi (*Trichoderma harzianum* and *Chaetomium globosum*) and three antagonist bacteria (*Pseudomonas putida*, *Bacillus subtilis*) used for the management of Alternaria leaf blight of Marigold (Priyanka *et al.* 2018; Abdel-Rahman, 2019 and Pun *et al.*, 2020) as well as the use of plant extracts had an effective role in combating the disease, as in the extract of cinnamon and cloves (Gupta and Prakash, 2021; Lengai *et al.*, 2021 and Ansary *et al.*, 2022). Cultural isolates of *Alternaria alternata* causing chrysanthemum leaf blight (Banne *et al.*, 2021). Cultural isolates of *Alternaria alternata* causing chrysanthemum leaf blight (Banne *et al.*, 2021). Leaf blight disease has severe impacts on Chrysanthemum, which results in invaded *Alteria alternata* that attacks mature leaves, with a rapid spread through plant tissues, soil, and surrounding air, especially under high temperature conditions (Liu, *et. al.* 2021). *A.alternata* can cause serious damage after infection by secreting fungus toxins and enzymes for cell wall degrading in Chrysanthemum tissues (Zhang *et. al* 2023). Leaf blight disease caused by *A.alternata* is considered one of the most damaging diseases leading to losses more than 80% in the yield and affects the quality of producing flowers (Magar *et. al.* 2022). *A.alternata*, a common fungus species is considered pathogenic in several

important crop plant (DeMers, 2022). The fungal diseases specially can cause considerable losses in productivity and quality as well as the medicinal value of *Chrysanthemum morifolium*, the fungus *Alteria* spp. can be destructive, causing black spot and leaf blight disease (Luo *et. al.* 2022).

Methodology

80 seeds samples of *Chrysanthemum parthenium* were obtained from 11 districts of Rajasthan. All the seed samples screened by the procedure as prescribed by ISTA (Anon, 1985). Two categories (asymptomatic and symptomatic) of seeds were analyzed by dry seed examination. Symptomatic seeds were further grouped into weakly and heavily infected seeds. Incubation test performed by standard Blotter method (SBM) and Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plate methods. For sterilization of seeds 2.0% hypochlorite solution were used (Pretreatment). Two seed samples (ac. Nos. 19 and 28) were used for histopathology and disease transmission studies.

Seed components *viz.* seedcoat (pericarp), aleurone layer and embryo were separated for component plating. 20 seeds/ category/ sample were soaked in water for 3h and then seed components were dissected and examined by SBM. 20 seeds/ category/ sample were used for clearwhole mount preparation. Dissociated seed components were boiled in 10% aqueous solution of KOH for 3-4 min then boiled in lectophenol cotton blue (20 min) and mounted in polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (Omar, Bolland and Heather, 1979). All the seed components were pressed gently under cover slip (Singh, Mathur, Neergaard, 1977). Exact location of the pathogen seed tissues was detected by microtome sectioning. 20 seeds of all categories of per sample were dipped in water and leave overnight. The seeds were submerged in 70% alcohol for 48h in vial, dehydrated through Tertiary-Butyl Alcohol (TBA) series, infiltrated and submerged in paraffin wax (merck). Blocks with embedded material were prepared. Thin cut sections were deparafinised and stained with saffranin and fastgreen than in cotton blue. The sections were mounted in DPX (Hohenson, 1940).

Result and Discussion

35 seed samples carried black discolouration on seed surface ranging from 0.75 – 10.25% incidence. On incubation the occurrence of *A.alternata* varied from 1-75% in untreated, 1-42% in pretreated seeds and 1-24% in PDA test.

The histopathological studies detected the location of the pathogen within the seed . In component plating of symptomatic seeds the infection was recorded on all the components of seeds. The incidence of pathogen varied from (25-75%) on pericarp, 15-30% on aleurone layer and 20-65% on embryo. The components were rotted due to growth of the pathogen. The mycelium of *A.alternata* was restricted to pericarp and recorded (10-15%) in both the samples (Table1). The characteristic septate inter and intra-cellular mycelium of the pathogen in observed by cleared wholemount preparation. Percentage range of infection was investigated from 20-55% in pericarp, 15-45% in aleurone layer and 15-50% in embryo (Table 1).

Percentage Infection of *Alternaria Alternata* In Different Parts of *Chrysanthemum* Seeds of Various Categories In Component Plating and Cleared Wholemount Preparations.

Component Plating

Ac. No.	ASYMPTOMATIC			SYMPTOMATIC					
				Weakly			Heavily		
	PC	AL	EMB	PC	AL	EMB	PC	AL	EMB
19	15	10	-	35	25	30	75	50	65
28	10	-	-	25	15	20	50	35	45

Cleared Wholemount Preparation

Ac. No.	ASYMPTOMATIC			SYMPTOMATIC					
				Weakly			Heavily		
	PC	AL	EMB	PC	AL	EMB	PC	AL	EMB
19	10	5	-	25	20	25	55	45	50
28	5	-	-	20	15	15	45	30	40

Thin sections of seeds were obtained by microtome sectioning. Presence of mycelium was noticed in outer layers of seed coat (Pericarp) of asymptomatic seeds. The weakly discoloured seeds showed hyphal bits in epicarp layer of pericarp (Fig 1 A, B). The pathogen observed in deeper ; layers of parenchyma of pericarp (Fig 1 C). The cells of parenchyma enlarged in size and filled with mycelia bits (Fig 1 D).Characteristic dark brown mycelium present in sclerenchymatous cells of pericarp (Fig 1 F). The embryo was normal and its cells were also normal looking.

The heavily discoloured seeds were deformed and poorly differentiated due to heavy infection. In pericarp, the epicarp layers carried hyphae. Parenchyma and schlerenchyma zone were completely disintegrated and replaced by hyphal mat. The embryo was completely deformed and carried mass of undifferentiated cells (Fig 1 D, F). Conidia observed in the region where tissue of embryo were disintegrated. The cells were small, dead, containing no cytoplasm and food content (Fig 2 D). In some seed sections the fungus formed characteristic beaded structure and hyphal clumps in embryonal tissues

(Fig 2 A, B). All the seed sections gave complete information on the seed-borne nature of *A.alternata*.

Fig 1: Histopathological studies on naturally infected chrysanthemum seed by *Alternaria alternata*.

1. A, B.T.S part of seed showing disintegration of epicarp layer and mycelium present in ridges and furrow of seed 125X, 125X.
2. C. T.S. part of seed showing inter- and intercellular mycelium in parenchymatous cells of pericarp region 250X, 500X.
3. D. T.S. part of seed showing disintegration and lysis of parenchymatous cells and hyphae present in cavities 250X.
4. E,F. T.S. part of seed showing hyphae in deeper layers of pericarp 250X.

Fig 2: Histopathological studies on naturally infected seed with *Alternaria alternata*.

1. T.S part of seed showing heavy infection in embryo. The cells are deformed due to mycelium clump 125X.
2. Same in high magnification 250X.
3. T.S. of whole seed heavily infected showing disintegration of cells of pericarp and embryo. The region is densely colonized by mycelium 50X.
4. Same in high magnification. Note distorted pericarp and undifferentiated embryo with dense growth of mycelium, Conidia of *A. alternata* are also found 125 X, 250X.

Disease Transmission

The symptoms caused by *A.alternata* appeared as browning and blackening of radical. Later the symptoms recognized as swollen hypocotyls. The disease progressed upward and caused rotting of cotyledonary leaves and finally mortality of seedlings occurred (Sharma, 1992).

In petriplate method, after 48h of incubation asymptomatic seeds get germinated (70-80%). But in symptomatic seeds germination was started on the 4th day and percentage was 45-45%; 30,36% in weakly and heavily infected seeds respectively in both sample. No seedling symptom was seen in asymptomatic category but infected seeds created mortality of seedlings which was 5,4% in weakly and 12,10% in heavily infected seeds. Ungerminated seeds covered with heavy growth of pathogen which was maximum in heavily infected seeds.

In water agar test infected seedlings showed symptoms as radical covered with growth of pathogen and appear black in colour and ultimately mortality of seedlings occurred. Total pre and post emergency losses were 43, 50% and 72-57% in weakly and heavily infected groups of both samples.

Conclusion

In present study *A.alternata* constituted as seed-borne pathogen. Characteristic mycelium was seen in vascular tissue of radical by clearing. The inoculum transmitted to seedling in water agar test and caused blackening of radicle and mortality of seedling. That was stated seed-borne nature of the pathogen. The pathogenic nature was reported in sunflower (Singh, Mathur and Neergaard, 1997). Microtome sectioning indicated that the fungus penetrates in seeds through pericarp. Neergaard (1979) states that seed coat is the common site of infection of most seed transmitted fungi. This brown inter and intracellular mycelium was mostly present in hypodermal cells of pericarp. Kumar, Manandhar and Sinclair (1986) also reported that hyphae of *A.alternata* was found in the seed parts *viz.* seed coat and endosperm of soyabean seeds. Embryo of heavily infected seeds were reduced in size and cells filled with mycelium of pathogen and became necrotic and dead. Sharma (1992) observed similar result induced by this fungus in seeds of taramira and linseed.

The seed-borne inoculum of *A.alternata* found mostly extraembryonal but in heavily infected seeds, intraembryonal infection was also observed. *A.alternata* has also been reported to be seed-borne in wheat (Agarwal et.al, 1987).

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